

Research Article

Online Peer-learning System for Architecture Course

Farah Hanna Ahmad Fuad^{1,*}, Adeeb Zulkifli², Mohamad Shahin Shahdan³, and Abdul Rahman Khamaruzaman⁴

¹ Department of Built Environment Studies and Technology, College of Built Environment, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Perak Branch, 32600, Seri Iskandar, Perak, MALAYSIA; fhanaafuad@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4024-6342

² Department of Built Environment Studies and Technology, College of Built Environment, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Perak Branch, 32600, Seri Iskandar, Perak, MALAYSIA; adeebzulkifli@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0009-0008-7476-1255

³ Department of Built Environment Studies and Technology, College of Built Environment, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Perak Branch, 32600, Seri Iskandar, Perak, MALAYSIA; mshahin@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0009-0008-7710-9561

⁴ Department of Built Environment Studies and Technology, College of Built Environment, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Perak Branch, 32600, Seri Iskandar, Perak, MALAYSIA; abdrahman@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0009-0002-1948-014X

* Correspondence: adeebzulkifli@uitm.edu.my; +60 19-674 0461

Abstract: Studio-based learning is grounded in project-based pedagogy. Regular tutorial and critiques sessions are crucial in order for students to further refine their ideas. However, with the hectic schedule, the time spent on the project often exceeded the formal learning hour which can lead to frustrations when students have no other support system or channel to rely on. Thus, the Peer-Learning System was created to promote skill development and knowledge sharing by utilizing the potential of digital platforms in architectural education, addressing the limitations of traditional learning models. Qualitative and quantitative methodology including surveys and focus groups were used. Findings shows that the Peer-Learning System satisfy the ease of access in terms of medium and time, easy to use, privacy protection and constructive interactions. This system of online peer-learning can be promoted to other recognized architecture courses in 21 universities across Malaysia.

Keywords: Studio-based learning; peer-learning; architecture course; digital platform.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Students in studio-based learning is often engaged in real-world design challenges in a project-based pedagogy as the method encourages experiential learning and critical thinking (Schön, 1983). Scheduled critiques are important to the studio environment in order to foster a culture of feedback that is essential for ideas development and refinement (Cuff, 1992). In addition, collaborative projects within studios promote teamwork and communication skills which are crucial for professional practice (Kvan, 2001). However, with the hectic schedule of studio-based students to handle multiple classes while the ongoing design project approaching deadlines, they are required to spend their time on the project, even out of the formal learning hour and lecturer's guidance, leading to student's frustrations due to absentees of other support system or channel to rely on. Thus, the Peer-Learning System is deemed suitable to promote skill development and knowledge sharing by utilizing the potential of

digital platforms in architectural education in order to address the limitations of traditional learning models. In contemporary education, the rise of technology has further expanded opportunities for peer learning, enabling global collaboration through online platforms (Garrison & Anderson, 2003).

The origins of peer-learning begin during ancient educational practices where in ancient Greece, the Socratic method encouraged dialogue among students to promote critical thinking and self-discovery (Ruderman, 1999). Similarly, in various cultures, apprenticeships allowed novices to learn skills through hands-on experience alongside skilled practitioners (Harris, 2009). These practices continued when the establishment of universities in Europe which incorporated collaborative learning through debates and study groups, highlighting the importance of peer interaction (Rüegg, 1992). In the 19th century, John Dewey emphasized experiential learning and collaboration by suggesting that students benefit significantly from interactions with their peers (Dewey, 1938). Peer interaction is also essential for cognitive development (Vygotsky, 1978).

In addition, architecture learning utilises graphic communications as it fulfils a number of purposes that improve knowledge and comprehension in the field. It requires the ability to visualize and communicate complex ideas by allowing students to translate their conceptual ideas into visual formats, such as sketches, diagrams, and models. By visualizing their designs, students can identify potential issues, assess functionality, and make informed revisions (Dodge, 2014). Thus, having a system online with the availability to express graphical information are highly recommended for studio-based courses especially in architectural design to mitigate potential miscommunication that can arise from text-based feedback alone.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Qualitative and quantitative methodology including focus groups and survey were used. According to Morgan (1998), focus groups typically consist of 6 to 12 participants who share relevant characteristics, allowing for diverse perspectives within a homogenous group. The session managed to gather 15 participants in the required focus group. The students involved are from semester 3 and semester 5 of Bachelor of Science (Hons.) Architecture (LAM/RIBA Part 1) in Universiti Teknologi MARA Perak Branch, Seri Iskandar campus. A 1-hour session was held by letting the participants to use the online system facilitated by the team members.

Figure 1. Focus group testing session

The Online Peer-learning System for Architecture Course uses MURAL platform as a medium. It allows participants to share and manipulate images, sketches, and diagrams in real time. This visual collaboration fosters a more engaging environment where ideas can be easily communicated and critiqued, allowing participants to annotate designs directly and provide immediate feedback. These advantages suit the studio-based pedagogy because the course needs visual representation to help

clarify and refine design concepts whilst making abstract ideas more concrete (Schön, 1983). Online questionnaire was distributed to the participants to gain feedbacks after the test session. In this survey, a mixed-methods approach will be employed, utilizing a combination of Likert scale and open-ended survey questions to gather comprehensive data. The Likert scale will consist of statements related to participants' satisfaction level, allowing respondents to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement on a five-point scale ranging from "poor" to "excellent". This quantitative measure will facilitate statistical analysis and provide insights into trends and patterns within the data. In addition to the structured Likert scale questions, open-ended survey questions are included for participants to express their positive and negative thoughts in their own words.

Figure 2. Peer- learning system using MURAL platform

3. FINDINGS

The findings of the survey provide valuable understandings into user satisfaction criteria of the focus group's participants. The study highlights overall satisfaction levels in term of medium accessibility, time accessibility, ease of use, privacy protection and constructive feedbacks. Open- ended questions regarding valuable features, and areas for improvement within the platform were also included.

3.1 Satisfaction Level

Figure 3. Satisfaction Level

In regards of satisfaction level attributes, highest percentage shows "excellent" satisfaction level in all terms including medium accessibility, time accessibility, ease of use, privacy protection and constructive feedbacks. Followed by "satisfactory" in term of medium accessibility and time

accessibility, whilst “very good” in term of constructive feedbacks. Only one student rated “poor” in term of privacy protection.

3.2.2 Overall Performance

Figure 4. Overall Performance

Overall, participants expressed a high level of satisfaction with the platform, with majority have rated their experience as "Excellent" or "Very Good."

3.2.3 Valuable Aspects

This table identifies the main themes and sub-themes regarding the valuable aspects of the system, along with illustrative quotes from participants.

Table 1. Thematic analysis on valuable aspects of the CoArch: Peer- Learning System platform

Theme	Sub- Theme	Example Quotes
Accessibility and Ease of Use	User-Friendly Interface	"Easy to consult"
	Navigation	"Easy navigation and clear"
Real-Time Interaction	Immediate Feedback	"Able to get feedback real-time"
	Enhanced Coaching	"Real-time movement makes coaching easier"
Collaboration and Engagement	Interaction with Peers and Instructors	"Able to interact with lecturers and seniors"
	Fun and Engaging Experience	"Fun to use"
Versatile Features	Image Uploading without Quality Loss	"Upload image without affecting quality"

3.2.3 Suggestion for Improvements

This table highlights areas where the system could be improved by capturing the major themes and sub-themes associated with participant quotes and suggestions for enhancements.

Table 2. Thematic analysis on Suggestion for Improvements of the CoArch: Peer- Learning System platform

Theme	Sub- Theme	Example Quotes
Technical Enhancements	Allow Video Uploads	"Allow video uploads."
Communication Improvements	Introduce Voice Features	"Use voice features for easier explanations."

	Real- time Notifications	"Add auto notifications for uploads."
Engagement and Interaction	Guideline for organizing	"Need to organize how students can comment on designs."
Privacy and Security	Enhance Privacy Measures	"Improve privacy and security of usage."

4. DISCUSSION

The data shows an overall indication of high satisfaction, especially among users who value features such as easy navigation and real-time feedback. Participants also noted significant aspects that they thought were helpful, such as the platform's collaborative features and ease of use. Participants emphasized that the platform's user-friendly interface and real-time feedback feature are especially helpful as they allow for instant communication all time around depending on the availability of user on the line. Numerous respondents are satisfied with the platform's accessibility for introverted users, indicating that it offers a welcoming setting for interaction. This aligns with research by Ricevuto & McLaughlin (2023), which suggests that well-designed online platforms can mitigate the challenges faced by introverted individuals in collaborative settings.

Several suggestions for enhancement emerged, indicating opportunities for further development, such as incorporate video upload capabilities and voice features to facilitate clearer communication and explanation of designs. However, this platform can be linked with existing Microsoft Team (MTeam), allowing students to add a shared digital canvas directly into any channel, chat, meeting invite, or live video meeting to acquire a better communication (www.mural.co). Some other recommendation highlights on introducing features like auto-notifications for new uploads, guideline for data organising and increase privacy measures. The thorough analysis aimed to guide future CoArch platform enhancements that will guarantee it satisfies the wide range of user needs.

5. CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, while many respondents found the platform effective for online interactions, the system is not a substitute for physical tutoring sessions. Overall, the feedback shows that CoArch: Peer- learning System for Architecture Course served its purpose to solve the limitations of traditional learning models, there is room for enhancements to further improve the user experience and address communication challenges. This system of online peer- learning can be used by other recognised architecture courses in 21 universities across Malaysia and other studio- based learning courses that utilizes graphic communication in their routine.

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